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MAED English 2A

Teaching Through Errors: Improving Students' Grammar

Learning a new language can be both exciting and challenging for students. When learning English, many students find it hard to use words and sentences the right way. This is because English has many rules, especially in morphology and syntax. Morphology is about how words are made, like adding endings such as “-s” or “-ed.” Syntax, on the other hand, is about how words are put together to make a correct sentence. These two are very important because they help us share our ideas clearly (Laurie Bauer, 2003). However, for learners, it is normal to make mistakes while trying to understand and use these rules. These mistakes are called learner errors, and they are a normal part of learning a language. S. P. Corder (1967) explains that errors are significant because they show that learners are actively learning the language. In the classroom, students often get confused when using verb tenses, subject-verb agreement, and sentence structure. Others may have a hard time with plural forms or using articles like “a,” “an,” and “the” correctly. These mistakes happen because students are still learning how English works. Sometimes, they also use rules from their first language, which may be different from English. Larry Selinker (1972) explains that learners develop an interlanguage, a system that is influenced by both their first language and the target language. Jack C. Richards (1974) also notes that many learner errors are caused by first language interference. Because of this, mistakes in morphology and syntax are very common, especially for beginners.

Even if these mistakes look like a problem, they actually show that students are learning. H. Douglas Brown (2007) states that errors are a natural and necessary part of language learning. When students try to use new words and sentence patterns, it is normal to make mistakes. These mistakes help teachers see what students already know and what they still need to improve. As Corder (1967) also explains, errors provide feedback to teachers about learners' progress. Instead of thinking that mistakes are bad, they should be seen as a step to better learning. By finding common mistakes, teachers can change the way they teach and explain lessons more clearly so students can understand better.

Teaching English can be hard, especially for new teachers who are still learning how to handle a class. When I worked as a substitute teacher handling Grade 9 students, I faced

many challenges inside the classroom. At first, I felt excited but also nervous because it was my first time teaching a group of students on my own. I thought that students at this level already understood most of the basic grammar rules in English. I expected that they could easily form correct sentences and use words properly. However, as the lessons went on, I realized that many of them were still having a hard time with simple grammar. Many students were confused about how to form words and how to arrange them in a sentence. Rod Ellis (2008) states that second language learners often struggle with grammatical forms and sentence structure. Some of them did not know when to use the correct verb tense, while others had trouble with subject-verb agreement. I also noticed that they sometimes used the wrong word forms or forgot to add endings like “-s” or “-ed.” Because of this, their sentences were often unclear or incorrect. It made me realize that learning English is not easy for them, and they still need more guidance and practice. This experience opened my eyes to the real situation inside the classroom. I understood that not all students learn at the same pace, and some need more time to understand the lesson. It also made me see that teaching is not just about explaining rules, but also about helping students understand in a simple and clear way. As a substitute teacher, I had to adjust my teaching style and be more patient so I could help my students learn better.

One of the main challenges I faced in teaching Grade 9 students was dealing with their common errors in morphology and syntax. These errors are about how students form words and how they put words together to make sentences. In simple terms, morphology focuses on the correct form of words, while syntax is about the correct order of words in a sentence. Many of these mistakes were seen in verb tenses, subject-verb agreement, sentence structure, and possessive forms. Heidi Dulay, Marina Burt, and Stephen Krashen (1982) state that such errors are common in second language learners. These areas are very important because they help students express their ideas clearly and correctly. When these are used the wrong way, the sentence can become confusing or hard to understand. I noticed that many students were not yet confident in using these basic grammar rules. Some of them were unsure about how to change verbs based on time, while others did not know how to match the subject with the correct verb. There were also students who had difficulty arranging words in the correct order, which affected the meaning of their sentences. In addition, some students did not understand how to show ownership using possessive forms. These problems showed that they were still learning and needed more practice and guidance. Because of these errors, it was sometimes difficult for students to express their thoughts clearly. Even if they had good ideas, their sentences were not always correct, which made their meaning unclear. This made me realize that I needed to explain the lessons in a simpler way and give more examples that they could easily understand. It also

showed me that these grammar skills should be taught step by step so students can build a stronger foundation in English.

To address these challenges, I used different ways of giving feedback and teaching that helped my students understand morphology and syntax better. One important way I used was giving immediate and clear corrective feedback. For example, when a student said “She go to school yesterday,” I did not just say it was wrong. Instead, I repeated the sentence in the correct way by saying, “She went to school yesterday,” so they could hear the right form. In this way, students can notice their mistakes and learn how to say the sentence correctly. According to Rod Ellis (2009), this kind of feedback helps students improve their accuracy when using a second language. Another strategy I used was modeling and guided practice. I first gave simple and clear examples, then I asked students to try on their own. For example, I wrote correct sentences on the board and explained why they were correct in very simple words. After that, I asked students to make their own sentences or answer practice activities. This step-by-step way helped them understand the lesson better and made it easier for them to follow. Lev Vygotsky (1978) supports this idea, saying that students learn better when the teacher guides and supports them during the learning process. I also used drills and repetition to help students remember grammar rules. For example, I asked them to repeat correct sentence patterns or practice changing verbs from present to past tense many times. Even if it seems simple, repeating the correct form helps students remember it better. According to B. F. Skinner (1957), practice and repetition are effective because they help students develop correct habits in learning. In addition, I used peer correction and group activities. I let students work in pairs or small groups to check each other’s sentences. This made them more active in class and helped them learn from one another. Sometimes, students feel more comfortable asking questions and learning with their classmates. As stated by H. Douglas Brown (2007), interactive activities help students learn better because they are more involved in the lesson. I made sure to use simple explanations and examples from their daily life. I used situations that they could easily understand, like school activities or daily routines. I also explained grammar rules using simple words and gave many examples before asking them to practice. This helped reduce their confusion and made the lesson easier to understand.

Students often made mistakes in verb tenses, which tell us when an action happens, like in the past, present, or future. I noticed that many students were confused about how to change verbs depending on time. For example, some students said “She go to school yesterday” instead of “She went to school yesterday.” This sentence is incorrect because the word “yesterday” shows that the action already happened in the past. Because of this, the verb should also be in the past form. The correct verb is “went,” not “go.” This kind of

mistake shows that students are still learning how verbs change based on time (Ellis, 2008). They may know the base form of the verb, but they are not yet sure how to change it when talking about the past or future. Because of this, they sometimes mix up verb forms and use the wrong one in their sentences. This can make their ideas unclear or confusing. That is why it is important for students to practice using the correct verb tense so they can express their ideas more clearly and correctly.

To help students improve their use of verb tenses, I used different kinds of corrective feedback and teaching strategies that are simple but effective. One helpful method is recasting, where the teacher repeats the student's sentence in the correct form without directly saying it is wrong. For example, when a student says "She go to school yesterday," I respond by saying, "She went to school yesterday." This helps students hear the correct form and notice their mistake. According to Rod Ellis (2008), this kind of corrective feedback helps learners improve their grammar because they become more aware of their errors. Another useful strategy is explicit correction with simple explanation. In this approach, I clearly tell the student what is wrong and explain it using easy words. For example, I say, "We use 'went' because 'yesterday' means it already happened." This helps students understand not just the correct answer, but also the reason behind it. Research by H. Douglas Brown (2007) shows that clear explanation supports better understanding of grammar rules. I also used guided practice and examples. First, I gave correct examples of sentences using different verb tenses. Then, I asked students to practice by changing verbs from present to past, or by making their own sentences. I guided them step by step until they became more confident. This is supported by Lev Vygotsky (1978), who explained that students learn better when they are guided by a teacher while practicing new skills. In addition, I used drills and repetition to help students remember the correct verb forms. For example, I asked them to repeat sentences or answer short exercises many times. This helped them become more familiar with how verbs change based on time. According to B. F. Skinner (1957), repetition helps strengthen learning because it builds correct habits. I also used real-life examples and simple activities. I asked students to talk about their daily activities, such as "What did you do yesterday?" This allowed them to practice using past tense in a meaningful way. When students use language in real situations, they understand it better and remember it longer.

There were also errors in subject-verb agreement, which means the subject and the verb must match. In simple terms, if the subject is one person or thing (singular), the verb should also be in singular form. I noticed that many students were confused about this rule. For example, some students wrote "He go to class every day" instead of "He goes to class every day." This sentence is incorrect because "he" is singular, so the verb should have an "-

s” at the end, making it “goes.” This kind of mistake shows that students are still learning how to match the subject with the correct verb (Dulay et al., 1982). They may understand the sentence, but they are not yet sure how to change the verb form. Because of this, they sometimes use the base form of the verb instead of the correct one. These errors can make sentences sound wrong, even if the idea is clear. That is why it is important for students to practice subject-verb agreement so they can form correct and clear sentences.

To help students improve their subject-verb agreement, I used different kinds of corrective feedback and teaching strategies that are simple and easy to follow. One helpful method is recasting, where I repeat the student’s sentence in the correct form. For example, when a student says “He go to class every day,” I respond by saying, “He goes to class every day.” This helps students hear the correct form without making them feel embarrassed. According to Rod Ellis (2009), this kind of feedback helps learners notice their mistakes and improve their grammar. Another strategy I used is explicit correction with simple explanation. In this method, I clearly tell the student what is wrong and explain it using easy words. For example, I say, “We use ‘goes’ because ‘he’ is one person, so the verb needs an ‘-s.’” This helps students understand both the rule and how to use it. H. Douglas Brown (2007) explains that clear explanations can help students better understand grammar rules. I also used guided practice and modeling. First, I showed correct examples on the board, such as “She eats,” “He runs,” and “The boy plays.” Then, I asked students to create their own sentences using the same pattern. I guided them step by step until they became more confident. This approach is supported by Lev Vygotsky (1978), who said that students learn better when they are supported by the teacher while practicing. In addition, I used drills and repetition to help students remember the rule. I asked them to repeat correct sentence patterns and answer short exercises many times. This helped them get used to adding “-s” to verbs when the subject is singular. According to B. F. Skinner (1957), repetition helps learners develop correct habits. I also used pair work and simple activities. I let students work with a partner to check each other’s sentences. I also gave fun activities like filling in blanks or correcting wrong sentences. This made learning more active and less stressful. As stated by H. Douglas Brown (2007), students learn better when they are actively involved in the lesson.

Another common problem was sentence structure, which is how words are arranged in a sentence. I noticed that some students placed words in the wrong order, which made their sentences sound strange or unclear. For example, some students said “Very tired I am today” instead of “I am very tired today.” This sentence is incorrect because English usually follows a simple pattern: subject + verb + other details. When students do not follow this correct order, the sentence can be confusing or sound unnatural, even if the words are

correct. This shows that they are still learning how to organize their ideas in English (Ellis, 2008). Because of this, it is important for students to practice forming sentences using the correct word order so they can communicate their thoughts more clearly.

To help students improve their sentence structure, I used different kinds of corrective feedback and teaching strategies that are simple and easy to understand. One helpful method is recasting, where I repeat the student's sentence in the correct order. For example, when a student says "Very tired I am today," I respond by saying, "I am very tired today." This allows students to hear the correct word order and compare it with their own sentence. According to Rod Ellis (2008), this kind of feedback helps learners notice their mistakes and improve their language use. Another strategy I used is explicit correction with clear explanation. I tell the students that the sentence is incorrect and explain why using simple words. For example, I say, "In English, we usually say the subject first, then the verb, and then the other details." This helps students understand the correct pattern of sentence structure. H. Douglas Brown (2007) explains that clear and simple explanations help students learn grammar more effectively. I also used modeling and guided practice. I wrote correct sentence patterns on the board, such as "I am happy," "She is tired," and "They are playing." Then, I asked students to follow the pattern and create their own sentences. I guided them step by step and corrected them when needed. This approach is supported by Lev Vygotsky (1978), who said that students learn better when they are supported by the teacher during practice. In addition, I used sentence-building activities. I gave students jumbled words and asked them to arrange the words into a correct sentence. This helped them practice the correct order in a fun and active way. I also used pair work, where students checked each other's sentences and helped fix mistakes. As stated by H. Douglas Brown (2007), interactive activities help students become more engaged in learning. Moreover, I used real-life examples and simple situations. I asked students to describe their feelings or daily activities using correct sentence structure. This helped them connect the lesson to their real life and made it easier for them to understand.

Lastly, students also had difficulty using possessive forms, which show ownership or who something belongs to. I noticed that many students were confused about how to use the apostrophe (') correctly. These mistakes show that students are still learning how to use possessive forms correctly (Bauer, 2003). They may know the words, but they are not yet sure how to show ownership in writing. Because of this, it is important for them to practice using apostrophes properly so they can make their sentences clearer and more accurate.

To help students improve their use of possessive forms, I used simple and clear corrective feedback and teaching strategies. One helpful method is recasting, where I repeat

the student's sentence in the correct form. For example, if a student says "students book," I respond by saying, "student's book" or "students' books," depending on the meaning. This helps students hear the correct use of the apostrophe and understand how ownership is shown. According to Rod Ellis (2009), this kind of feedback helps learners notice their mistakes and improve their language use. Another strategy I used is explicit correction with simple explanation. I clearly explain the rule in easy words. For example, I say, "We use 's when something belongs to one person, and s' when it belongs to many people." This helps students understand how to use apostrophes correctly. H. Douglas Brown (2007) states that clear explanations can help students better understand grammar rules. I also used modeling and guided practice. I wrote examples on the board, such as "Maria's bag," "the teacher's book," and "the students' classroom." Then, I asked students to make their own sentences using the same pattern. I guided them step by step and corrected them when needed. This approach is supported by Lev Vygotsky (1978), who explained that students learn better with teacher support. In addition, I used practice activities and drills. I gave exercises where students needed to add apostrophes in the correct place or choose the correct form. Repeating these activities helped them remember the rules. According to B. F. Skinner (1957), repetition helps learners develop correct habits. Lastly, I used real-life examples and simple situations. I asked students to talk about things they own, like "my friend's phone" or "my parents' house." This made the lesson more meaningful and easier to understand.

In conclusion, learning English can be both difficult and meaningful, especially when students are still learning how to use correct word forms and sentence structure. Many students make mistakes in morphology and syntax, such as in verb tenses, subject-verb agreement, sentence structure, and possessive forms. These mistakes may seem like a problem at first, but they are actually a normal part of learning. They show that students are trying to understand the language and use it in their own way. As explained by different researchers, learner errors are important because they help teachers see the progress of students and identify what they still need to improve. Instead of seeing mistakes as something negative, they should be seen as a sign that learning is happening. With time, practice, and proper guidance, students can slowly correct these errors and improve their skills in using English. My experience as a substitute teacher helped me understand how important it is to be patient, flexible, and supportive when teaching students. I learned that students need simple explanations, clear examples, and enough practice to fully understand grammar rules. By giving corrective feedback, guiding them step by step, and using activities that are easy to understand, I was able to help my students improve little by little. I also realized that every student learns in a different way and at a different pace, so it is important to adjust teaching strategies to meet their needs. Overall, teaching English is not just about

correcting mistakes, but about helping students build confidence and express their ideas clearly. In the end, mistakes are not failures, but important steps in becoming better learners and more effective communicators.

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